

DESIGN & FABRICATION OF PADDLE OPERATED MULTI-POINT PESTICIDE SPRAYING MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

We all know that in today's scenario the poor farmers are facing many problems in farming. So through this project we want to compensate this problem up to some extent. With the help of these technical syntheses, we have tried to help the poor farmers of mother land India by reducing their effort.

Key words: - Pedal operated multipoint pesticide sprayer, Ergonomics, Pressure and Nozzle.

INTRODUCTION

The project is carried out for design & fabrication of pesticide spraying machine used for the agricultural purpose. The manually operated multipoint sprayer pump is worked by operating a pedal lever by the operator. It requires one person to work. The spray liquid is kept in bucket or container and it is sucked by a suction hose through a filter (strainer) due to piston movement used in the bicycle.

The multi point operated spraying machine is basically for crop spraying in the farm. The design should be strong and sturdy which implement work effectively. For spraying farms in present era, a person use hand operated pumping machine which is time consuming & costly, which needs more human efforts. It is difficult to treat field crops by foot sprayers because the sprayer is kept on ground and pesticide solution tank is also kept on ground separately and so movement of the long delivery hose becomes very difficult. If large area can be covered for spraying, using less efforts & time, this implants new concept in design engineering. So, in consideration of all the above problems we wish to fabricate such equipment which minimise human efforts & saves the time without using any power sources

LITERATURE REVIEW:-

Sandeep H. Poratkar, Dhanraj R. Raut, [1] in paper entitled "Development of multi nozzle pesticides sprayer pump" says that, the suggested model have no need to carry the tank on back, Increase the spraying rate and better performance.

Shivaraja kumar & Parameswaramurthy[2] suggested in their paper entitled "Design And Development Of Wheel And Pedal Operated Sprayer" that the wheel and pedal operated sprayer is manly low cost and easy to move in the farms and also improves the quality of spraying pesticides. The operator can cover two parallel rows simultaneously without any additional energy being used as well as it reduces the fatigue of the operator.

Joginder Singh[3] in the paper entitled "Scope, Progress and Constraints of Farm Mechanization in India" says, Mechanization in Indian agriculture is the need of the time but its use has to be viewed from angles of unemployment problems of human and animal force and vast majority of small and uneconomical farms.

Paul E. Sumner [4] having paper entitled “Hand-held and Backpack Sprayers for Applying Pesticides.” that, Hand sprayer skilled operators is to achieve a uniform broadcast application. A simple and quick test is to spray an area on a paved surface with water in your normal spraying manner on a warm day.

David McAuliffe and Vanessa P. Gray [5] having paper entitled “Application technology: Problems and opportunities with Knapsack sprayer, Including the cf valves or Constant Flow Valves.” Says, the lever operated knapsack sprayers continues to be the most common piece of application equipment for crop protection in many countries. Its versatility in use with a variety of different chemical products and its relative ease of operation make it well suited for small-scale growers aiming to increase agricultural productivity

AIM / OBJECTIVE:-

Our main aim is to help the poor farmers by reducing their effort in agriculture field by the help of this bicycle operated spraying machine, which is affordable and much more efficient than other spraying machine.

Objectives-

- 1)It is Eco-friendly.
- 2)It saves money as compared to other spraying machines.
- 3)It serves the dual use of sprayer cum bicycle.
- 4)It is easy to transport from one place to another.
- 5)No use of fossil fuel.

Much more efficient than other spraying machine

Requirement of Design:-

The Indian farmers (small, marginal, small and marginal, semi-medium) are currently using lever operated backpack sprayer. A backpack sprayer consists of tank 10 -20 liter capacity carried by two adjustable straps. Constant pumping is required to operate this which results in muscular disorder. Also, the backpack sprayer can't maintain pressure, results in drifts/dribbling. Developing adequate pressure is laborious and time consuming Pumping to operating pressure is also time consuming. Moreover, very small area is covered while spraying. So, more time are required to spray the entire land. Back pain problems may arise during middle age due to carrying of 10-20 litre tanks on back.

In our propose design we are take care of upcoming problem while using backpack sprayer. The operating and design is simple that can handle every person. We are trying to helping the farmer for easy to farming. That's why we create multipoint pesticide spraying machine. By this machine the farmer can gives his less effort and finish his work in short time. While using our machine, the farmer does not need to protect his face for entering pesticide particle in the body while birthing.

Fig1: - CAD Design of Multipoint Pesticide spraying machine

METHODOLOGY:-

1. Reciprocating compressor

A reciprocating compressor or piston compressor is a positive-displacement compressor that uses pistons driven by a crankshaft to deliver gases at high pressure.

The intake gas enters the suction manifold, then flows into the compression cylinder where it gets compressed by a piston driven in a reciprocating motion via a crankshaft, and is then discharged. Applications include oil refineries, gas pipelines, chemical plants, natural gas processing plants and refrigeration plants. One specialty application is the blowing of plastic bottles made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET).

2. Nozzle

Nozzle comprises of the outlet of reservoir system. It is the main part of a mechanism which sprays the pesticide.

3. Sprockets

A sprocket or sprocket-wheel is a profiled wheel with teeth, cogs, or even sprockets that mesh with a chain, track or other perforated or indented material.

The name "sprocket" applies generally to any wheel upon which are radial projections that engage a chain passing over it. It is distinguished from a gear in that sprockets are never meshed together directly, and differs from a pulley in that sprockets have teeth and pulleys are smooth. Sprockets are used in bicycles, motorcycles, cars, tracked vehicles, and other machinery either to transmit rotary motion between two shafts where gears are unsuitable or to impart linear motion to a track, tape etc. Perhaps the most common form of sprocket may be found in the bicycle, in which the pedal shaft carries a large sprocket-wheel, which drives a chain, which, in turn, drives a small sprocket on the axle of the rear wheel. Early automobiles were also largely driven by sprocket and chain mechanism, a practice largely copied from bicycles.

4. Chain

Roller chain or bush roller chain is the type of chain drive most commonly used for transmission of mechanical power on many kinds of domestic, industrial and agricultural machinery, including conveyors, wire- and tube-drawing machines, printing presses, cars, motorcycles, and bicycles. It consists of a series of short cylindrical rollers held together by side links. It is driven by a toothed wheel called a sprocket. It is a simple, reliable, and efficient means of power transmission.

Though Hans Renold is credited with inventing the roller chain in 1880, sketches by Leonardo da-Vinci in the 16th century show a chain with a roller bearing.

5. Storage tank

Storage tanks are containers that hold liquids, compressed gases (gas tank) or mediums used for the short- or long-term storage of heat or cold. The term can be used for reservoirs (artificial lakes and ponds), and for manufactured containers. The usage of the word tank for reservoirs is common or universal in American English and moderately common in British English. In other countries, the term tends to refer only to artificial containers.

Storage tanks are available in many shapes: vertical and horizontal cylindrical; open top and closed top; flat bottom, cone bottom, slope bottom and dish bottom. Large tanks tend to be vertical cylindrical, or to have rounded corners transition from vertical side wall to bottom profile, to easier withstand hydraulic hydrostatically induced pressure of contained liquid. Most container tanks for handling liquids during transportation are designed to handle varying degrees of pressure.

Working:-

Hand lever operated sprayer having the mechanical energy for driving. The input is given through the lever to hand lever operated sprayer and in proposed model input given through the pedal that is easy to given through pedal. As soon as the cycle is drive. This portable spraying system consists of an adjustable boom, tank, chain and sprockets and crank shaft mechanism for converting rotary motion to reciprocating motion. The assembly can be mounted on any bicycle available in the market. A cylindrical tank containing the solution is firmly attached to the frame of the bicycle. While the bicycle is pulled forward, the cam follower provides reciprocating motion to pump, which compresses the fluid in the tank. This comes out through the spraying nozzle, connected to boom, as mist.

Fig:-Blog Diagram of Power Transmission

First of all we need to create the pressure in the small tank which having 3lit capacity, for that purpose we need to drive the pedal at one place with the all nozzle closed on the stand. Once the pressure creates in the small tank it maintains and we can easy drive the bicycle through the farm. When cycle providing input from the pedal to standard sprocket which is on the back wheel of cycle as the another sprocket having OD 158 mm ,number of teeth 42 which is fixed on the same shaft of the. As the rotation receives that sprocket it transfers to pinion having OD 49 mm number of teeth 13 with the help of chain.

The difference of the sprocket and pinion helps in the proving the speed. The crank shaft arrangement placed on the same shaft the pinion place, the pinion gives his rotation to that crank shaft. Here the rotary motion is converted into reciprocating with the help of piston having 150mm stroke, Ø100mm. Just on the piston the pump is placed having non-return valve which helps to create pressure in the tank nearly 13.5 psi pressure can be created in the small tank having the capacity of 3lit. Piston pumps having the two outputs and one input. The input is attached to the larger tank contain solution of pesticide and two outputs are help to cover the larger area in the less time.

This sprayer is energy-efficient and easy to operate and maintain. As it is a flexible product with adjustable height and width of spraying boom there is greater flexibility for using it for various crops. Since the bicycle requires less space to move, it can be used in a more versatile manner as compared to power sprayers that are mounted on tractors. A labour saving device, it can be used to spray one acre of land in 45 minutes thus covering more area compared to manual spraying. Easy to assemble and dissemble, it serves the dual use of sprayer cum bicycle.

Fig:- Arrangement of piston, pump, small tank, sprocket and pinion through chain

SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK:-

In future it can be used to generate electricity by connecting dynamometer at rear wheel of bicycle. This mechanism can also be used for winnowing. Power transmission to other sources, which can transfer manual work to machine work. Use of positive drive utilizes total power consumption for various farming functions in different types of equipment. Multi-operational Machine can designed using such concept of mechanism.

Calculation for pressure:-

Replicate	Volume of water collected (lts)
1	1.4
2	1.48
3	1.3
4	1.42

Table 1:-Data collection for the sprayer calculation

Time consumed= 60 Seconds

Average volume flow out from the implement = $(1.4+1.48+1.3+1.42)/4$
= **1.4 lit**

Amount of water flow out from the implement per second=
 $1.4/60$
= 0.023 lit/sec

For per minute
= $0.023/60$
= **3.89×10^{-4} lit/min**

Application rate

F = SDA/10000

Where,

F = Flow rate *ltr/min*

S = swath width in meter (inner diameter of plastic pipe)

D = Operator walking speed in M/min

A = Application rate in *ltr/ha*

Operate walking speed = *5km/hr*

$3.89 = (7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot 30 \cdot 10^3 \cdot A) / 10000$

A = 185.238 lit/hactor

A = 75.60 lit/ acer

Sr.No.	Components	Dimension
1	Sprocket	OD 158mm, Teeth 42
2	Pinion	OD 49mm, Teeth 23
3	Chain	2.5 feet
4	Bearing	Bearing Number(62004)
5	Bearing Housing	In Triangular Shape
6	Bearing Shaft	OD 15mm
7	Pulley	OD 96mm
8	Piston Pump	1
9	Pump 's Tank Capacity	3 lit
10	Plastic Water Tank Capacity	30 lit (250 X250X400 mm)
11	Spraying Nozzle:- Turbo Flood Jet Nozzle	4
12	Hand Clutch	1
13	Spraying Boom	4 feet
14	Hand Leaver spray with clutches	OD=10mm, Length=2 feet
15	Plastic Pipe	10 feet(ID 7mm X OD 11 mm)
16	Branch Tree	4 no. ¼" X ¼"

Table:-Dimension Of component

CONCLUSION:-

The pedal operated sprayer is fabricated in low cost and easy to handle in the farms and also improves the quality of spraying pesticides. The operator can cover large area without any additional energy by using the bicycle for a spraying purpose by converting its circular motion into reciprocating motion of reciprocating compressor as well as it reduces the fatigue of the operator. This project is ergonomically designed. Ergonomically it is very useful to minimize the effort while spraying the pesticide also the process saves the time & improve the performance.

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